

MEDICAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF LIPID AND CARBOHYDRATE METABOLISM CHARACTERISTICS IN PATIENTS WITH ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE AFTER REVASCULARIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Objective. To study the contribution to the determination of residual risk in patients with coronary artery disease (CAD) after myocardial revascularization, from the perspective of carbohydrate and fat metabolism.

Materials and methods. The study included 115 patients with IHD who underwent percutaneous coronary interventions and/or aortocoronary bypass surgery. Depending on the presence of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), patients were divided into two groups: without T2DM (n=59) and with T2DM (n=56). All patients underwent clinical and laboratory examinations to determine lipid profile and carbohydrate metabolism indicators, biomarkers of inflammation and endothelial dysfunction, as well as instrumental methods (ECG, echocardiography, tissue Doppler imaging, renal artery Doppler imaging).

Results. It was found that patients with IHD and T2DM had more pronounced lipid and carbohydrate metabolism disorders: increased triglyceride levels, decreased HDL cholesterol, increased HbA1c, and increased platelet aggregation activity. These changes were accompanied by worse endothelial function and a higher Gensini score, indicating severe coronary artery disease. Lipid and carbohydrate metabolism disorders were significantly associated with the development of endothelial dysfunction and renal disorders, increasing residual cardiovascular risk.

Conclusion. Lipid and carbohydrate disorders are key components of residual risk in patients with IHD after myocardial revascularization. The identification of these disorders should be taken into account when developing personalized secondary prevention strategies.

Keywords: ischemic heart disease, type 2 diabetes mellitus, lipid metabolism, carbohydrate metabolism, residual risk, myocardial revascularization.

Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) continue to be among the leading causes of death worldwide. According to the WHO, more than 17 million people die from CVD each year, and about 85% of these cases are associated with coronary heart disease (CHD) and stroke [1]. Despite significant advances in the treatment of CHD, including the introduction of myocardial revascularization techniques and the widespread use of statins, many patients remain at high residual risk of adverse cardiovascular events [2].

Key factors contributing to residual risk are considered to be disorders of lipid and carbohydrate metabolism. Even when target LDL-C levels are achieved with statin therapy, the incidence of cardiovascular complications remains high, which is associated with

atherogenic dyslipidemia (increased triglycerides, decreased HDL, increased lipoprotein remnants) and insulin resistance [3,4].

These disorders are particularly significant in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). According to the International Diabetes Federation, by 2035, the number of people with T2DM worldwide will exceed 600 million [5]. The combination of T2DM and CHD increases the risk of recurrent heart attacks, heart failure, and death by 4–5 times [6]. T2DM is considered equivalent to cardiovascular risk, and control of metabolic disorders in this category of patients is of fundamental importance [7].

Despite the active use of modern secondary prevention regimens, including dual antiplatelet therapy, RAAS inhibitors, and lipid-lowering drugs, patients with IHD and T2DM have a high incidence of endothelial dysfunction, progression of atherosclerosis, and

kidney damage [8,9]. This confirms the presence of unresolved residual risk, the most important determinants of which are dyslipidemia and carbohydrate metabolism disorders. In this regard, studying the role of lipid and carbohydrate disorders in the formation of residual risk in patients with coronary artery disease after myocardial revascularization is a pressing task of significant clinical and prognostic importance.

The aim of the study was to evaluate the role of lipid and carbohydrate metabolism disorders in the formation of residual risk in patients with IHD after myocardial revascularization.

Materials and methods

A total of 115 patients with coronary artery disease (CAD) who underwent myocardial revascularization (percutaneous coronary intervention and/or aorto-coronary bypass grafting) were observed. The average age of the patients was 65 years (range 45 to 87 years).

Depending on the presence of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), patients were divided into two groups: Group 1 (n=59) — patients with IHD without T2DM;

Group 2 (n=56) — patients with IHD and T2DM.

The groups were comparable in terms of clinical and anthropometric characteristics.

All patients underwent a standard clinical examination: collection of complaints, medical history, clinical examination, measurement of blood pressure and heart rate.

Laboratory tests included: determination of fasting glucose levels and 2 hours after a meal; glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c); lipid profile indicators: total cholesterol (TC), low-density lipoproteins (LDL), high-density lipoproteins (HDL), triglycerides (TG); markers of endothelial dysfunction and inflammation: endothelin-1 (ET-1), interleukin-6 (IL-6), vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF); assessment of platelet aggregation activity.

The following instrumental methods were performed: electrocardiography (ECG); echocardiography with assessment of systolic and diastolic function of the left ventricle; tissue myocardial Doppler imaging; renal artery Doppler imaging; vascular wall stiffness testing.

Study results: The study included 115 patients with IHD (mean age 65 ± 9 years; 68% male). Patients were divided into 2 groups: group 1 — patients with IHD without DM2 (n=59), group 2 — IHD with DM2 (n=56). The groups were comparable in terms of age and BMI (29.1 ± 3.8 and 30.4 ± 4.1 kg/m², respectively; p>0.05).

More pronounced changes were observed in group 2 (IHD+DM2): triglyceride levels were higher (2.32 ± 0.64 mmol/L vs. 1.78 ± 0.52 mmol/L; p<0.01), and HDL concentration was lower (0.91 ± 0.24 mmol/L vs. 1.14 ± 0.27 mmol/L; p<0.05). Total cholesterol and LDL levels remained elevated in both groups, with no significant differences (p>0.05). These data confirm the presence of atherogenic dyslipidemia in patients with T2DM, which is a component of residual risk [10,11].

In patients with T2DM, carbohydrate metabolism indicators were significantly worse: HbA1c was 8.1 ± 1.2% versus 5.6 ± 0.4% (p<0.001), fasting blood glucose was 8.7 ± 2.3 mmol/L versus 5.1 ± 0.7 mmol/L (p<0.001). HbA1c levels correlated positively with platelet aggregation (r=0.45; p<0.01), confirming the role of hyperglycemia in the development of a pro-thrombotic state [12–14].

When studying endothelial function and vascular stiffness, it was found that patients with IHD+DM2 had a decrease in endothelium-dependent vasodilation of the brachial artery (5.8 ± 1.7% vs. 8.9 ± 2.2%; p<0.01), an increase in endothelin-1 levels (3.1 ± 0.7 pg/ml vs. 2.4 ± 0.5 pg/ml; p<0.05) and VEGF, as well as an increase in pulse wave velocity, indicating more pronounced endothelial dysfunction and arterial stiffness [15–17].

Table 1.

Lipid metabolism indicators in the study groups

Index	Comparison group (n=59)	Main group(n=56)	p
TC, mmol/l	5,41 ± 1,13	5,63 ± 1,21	0,32
LPLD, mmol/l	3,23 ± 0,89	3,23 ± 1,01	0,44
LPHD, mmol/l	1,14 ± 0,27	0,91 ± 0,24	<0,05
TG, mmol/l	1,78 ± 0,52	2,32 ± 0,64	<0,01

The Gensini score was significantly higher in group 2 (68 ± 14 vs. 52 ± 11; p<0.01). It correlated positively with HbA1c (r=0.417; p<0.01) and triglycerides (r=0.351; p<0.05), confirming the influence of metabolic disorders on the progression of coronary atherosclerosis.

Table 2.

Carbohydrate metabolism indicators

Index	Comparison group (n=59)	Main group(n=56)	p
Fasting glucose, mmol/l	5,07 ± 0,69	8,67 ± 2,29	<0,001
HbA1c, %	5,76 ± 0,41	8,14 ± 1,21	<0,001

Discussion: Our results showed that patients with IHD and T2DM continue to have significant lipid and carbohydrate metabolism disorders even after successful revascularization. The presence of atherogenic dyslipidemia (elevated TG, reduced HDL) and chronic hyperglycemia confirm that these factors play a leading role in the formation of residual risk. These results are consistent with large clinical studies. For example, the

REDUCE-IT study showed that patients with high TG levels remain at risk of cardiovascular complications even with statin therapy [12]. Elevated HbA1c is also an independent predictor of adverse outcomes: data from the UKPDS and subsequent meta-analyses have shown that each 1% increase in HbA1c increases the risk of vascular complications by 18% [13,14].

Endothelial dysfunction, confirmed by a decrease in FEVO and an increase in endothelin-1, reflects impaired regulation of vascular tone. Similar data were obtained in studies by Anderson et al. and Vlachopoulos et al., where endothelial dysfunction and vascular stiffness were considered universal mechanisms for increasing residual risk [15–17].

A higher Gensini score in patients with T2DM demonstrates that the combination of dyslipidemia and hyperglycemia leads to more severe coronary artery disease. The association of the score with impaired renal function emphasizes the systemic nature of the atherosclerotic process.

Modern approaches to reducing residual risk include the use of additional therapeutic strategies. SGLT2 inhibitors (empagliflozin, dapagliflozin) reduce cardiovascular mortality and the risk of hospitalizations for heart failure [18]. GLP-1 agonists (semaglutide, liraglutide) have been shown to be effective in reducing the incidence of myocardial infarction and stroke [19]. New lipid-lowering drugs — PCSK9 inhibitors, ezetimibe, omega-3 fatty acids — allow for the correction of residual lipid metabolism disorders [4,12].

Thus, our data confirm the need for a comprehensive assessment of metabolic status in patients with IHD after myocardial revascularization and the implementation of personalized secondary prevention regimens focused not only on LDL but also on the correction of atherogenic dyslipidemia and hyperglycemia.

Conclusion: Lipid and carbohydrate metabolism disorders are the most important factors of residual risk in patients with coronary artery disease after myocardial revascularization. Our study shows that patients with T2DM have more pronounced manifestations of atherogenic dyslipidemia, inadequate glycemic control, and endothelial dysfunction, which is accompanied by more severe coronary artery disease and decreased vascular wall elasticity.

Even with standard therapy (statins, antiplatelet agents, RAAS inhibitors), adverse metabolic changes persist, increasing residual risk. This highlights the need to expand secondary prevention strategies in this category of patients, including the use of modern lipid-lowering and hypoglycemic agents capable of exerting pleiotropic effects and reducing residual risk.

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